

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**OCCURENCE OF THE SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA OF
THE HEAD AND NECK**¹Dr Raja Gulam Mujtaba, ²Dr Umer Abid Mughal, ³Dr Muhammad Ishfaq¹Abass Institute of Medical Sciences Muzaffarabad, ²Chandka Medical College Larkana, ³BHU
Hoot Wala Jalalpur Pirwala**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Objective: To determine the risk of factors involved in order to promote the education of the community for better prevention of the disease.

Material and Methods: This study was conducted at AIMS hospital and the duration of this study was from July 2019 to March 2020. 98 patients were the participants of this study. The mean age of patients is 51 ± 9.31 years the enrolled 55% of patients were male and 45% females. Among the patients enrolled for the study, 66% were from urban areas and 34% belonged to rural areas.

Conclusion: Head and Neck squamous carcinoma is the most common form of tumor in Head and Neck ___ region. The most common site is hypopharynx and the most important risk factor is smoking. The highest incidence of the disease in 5th decade. Head and Neck tumor comprises Neoplastic growth of the oral cavity including Nasal cavity, Pharyngeal cavity, salivary glands, lips and Paranasal sinuses. HNC (head and neck carcinoma) comprises 6% of total tumors of the world. 110,000 patients are diagnosed with HNC in Europe/year.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Raja Gulam Mujtaba**

Abass Institute of Medical Sciences Muzaffarabad.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Raja Gulam Mujtaba et al, **Occurence Of The Squamous Cell Carcinoma Of The Head And Neck** ., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2021; 08[1].

INTRODUCTION:

Head and neck cancers are classified together with justification of epidemiology, Risk factors, similar natural history, control measures and morphology. Squamous cell carcinoma is the most common of all accounting for 22% of Asian burden of cancers. A study Locally done on the trends of the cancer patients shows 2 years' survival rate to be 71% diagnosed between 2012-2016. Another study shows the 2 years' average survival rate to be 63%. Another study done a few years back in Mayo hospital reported the average 2-year survival rate to be 71%. it may be variable depending on the stage and grade of the disease.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted at AIMS hospital and the duration of this study was from July 2019 to March 2020. 98 patients were enrolled in the study biopsies were taken and sent to histopathology lab for diagnosis and squamous cell carcinoma was reported. Data was taken about gender, age, and smoking history. Histological diagnoses were acquired from the pathology lab. Data was collected and analyzed by SPSS 19. Means were taken for quantitative variables and percentage were taken for qualitative variables.

RESULTS:

Mean age of patients is 51 ± 9.31 . Median age is 54 years. Mean age of females was 45.73 ± 3.32 . 56% patients were from rural areas and 44% were from urban side. Smoking history was present in 58% of cases while 23% suffered from iron deficiency among 5% the history positive for Pan chewing and 5% were Alcoholics. Rest of the cases showed No identifiable cause. Females from the villages suffered slightly more than urban areas females may be due to nutritional deficiency. On histopathology it was revealed that 57% patients had well differentiated carcinoma while 21% suffered from moderately differentiated and 22% showed poor differentiation on histopathology.

DISCUSSION:

The Head and Neck malignancies have different incidences in different parts of the world [1]. Pakistan is among the countries having high incidence for this disease due to increased Betel Nut, Pan chewing and smoking [2]. Our study shows almost same proportion of males and females who suffered from the disease. The most common site for the cancer is hypopharynx. Another study done in Lahore shows the same ratio of Females to males and the most common site was reported to be hypopharynx in their study [3]. A study in India Bihar, shows Hypo pharyngeal carcinoma to be the third most common carcinoma our study shows

larynx to be the 2nd commonest site of carcinoma head and neck [4]. While another study done at Multan shows Larynx is the most common site of Head and Neck malignancies [5].

In our study it is reported that the females presented earlier as compared to their counterparts in age with the disease probably due to poor nutritional statuses of the females in our country. The areas having increased betel Nut use and tobacco smoking have increased Risk of HNC [6]. Our study shows 10% of cases of cancer have oral cavity or oro-Pharyngeal tumors. While another study done in Africa shows HNC constitute 88% of cancer burden [7].

CONCLUSION:

Pakistan falls in the category of high risk for Head and Neck malignancies. It is due to Not up to mark health education of patients. Risk factors like smoking, betel Nut, Pan chewing and malnutrition are increasing the burden of the disease. moreover, Late presentation and Non-Optimum treatment are the causes for the poor prognosis of the patients. proper health education and up to mark health care must be given to patients to put a control on the rising incidence of Head and neck carcinoma.

REFERENCES:

1. Nelson, T.G. and R.E. Ashton, Low incidence of metastasis and recurrence from cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma found in a UK population: Do we need to adjust our thinking on this rare but potentially fatal event? *Journal of surgical oncology*, 2017. 116(6): p. 783-788.
2. Akinshipo, A.-W.O., et al., Head and neck cancers: An histopathologic review of cases seen in three Tertiary Hospitals in Northwestern Nigeria. *Journal of Clinical Sciences*, 2017. 14(3): p. 113.
3. Hamiter, M., et al., A pilot study of Merkel cell polyomavirus in squamous cell carcinoma of the tongue. *Oral oncology*, 2017. 74: p. 111-114.
4. Sundermann, B.V., et al., The localization and risk factors of squamous cell carcinoma in the oral cavity: A retrospective study of 1501 cases. *Journal of Cranio-Maxillo-Facial Surgery*, 2018. 46(2): p. 177-182.
5. Platek, A.J., et al., The association of lifetime physical inactivity with head and neck cancer: a hospital-based case-control analysis. *European Archives of Oto-Rhino-Laryngology*, 2017. 274(10): p. 3773-3780.
6. Minhas, S., et al., Concomitant-chemoradiotherapy-associated oral lesions in patients with oral squamous-cell carcinoma. *Cancer biology & medicine*, 2017. 14(2): p. 176.

7. Schmitt, J., et al., Is ultraviolet exposure acquired at work the most important risk factor for cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma? Results of the population-based case-control study FB-181.

British Journal of Dermatology, 2018. 178(2): p. 462-472.